

THE DEVELOPMENT OF E-MEDIATION IN EUROPE AND IN THE REST OF THE WORLD: A COMPARATIVE APPROACH AND THE REASONS FOR A DOUBLE SPEED³

Abstract. — 1. Introductory remarks on the features of ADR/ODR as a form of justice within the framework of E.U. — 2. Mediation: Concepts and controversial aspects. — 3. E-mediation: origin and current development. — 4. The development of consumer's e-mediation within the EU. — 5. E-mediation: the common law experience. — 5.1 U.S.A. — 5.2 Canada. — 5.3 Australia. — 5.4. U.K. — 6. The reason for the European traditional scepticism on e-mediation and the lesson to be learned from common law systems. — 7. Conclusions.

Abstract

The principal objective of the current study is to thoroughly examine the role of e-mediation and online dispute resolution as valuable tools for resolving legal disputes in civil and commercial matters and the reasons why this remedy is growing at a slower speed in Europe than in the rest of the world. To this end, this paper gives an overview of the concept of 'mediation' in the context of alternative dispute resolutions (ADRs) and its status in the context of e-mediation in general. Then, this study provides an overview of the historical origin and worldwide practices concerning e-mediation to understand the reasons behind its greater development in the countries where it originated: U.S.A., Canada, Australia and the UK. The work finally briefly analyses the perspectives for the development of e-mediation in Europe and in the rest of the world. The reason for the two rates of development of those systems is to be identified in the specific worry that European systems have about balancing the privatisation of justice with the guarantee of fundamental rights, especially concerning an effective access to justice.

1. *Introductory remarks on the features of ADR/ODR as a form of justice within the framework of the E.U.* — The emergence of alternative dispute resolution (ADR)⁴ and online dispute resolution (ODR) have challenged our perception of 'access to justice'. The term ADR refers to all those extra-judicial mechanisms of dispute settlement through which the parties may, upon their choice, reach an agreement producing a result like that of the cognisance process with the effect of solving an existing dispute. As a result of these alternative methods - and in particular of ODR - access to justice is no longer restricted to access to physical courts⁵, with the effect of reducing the importance of the requirement of physical proximity in litigation (something that emerged in the discussions concerning the "Corona crisis measures", blocking not only the normal functioning of societies, but also of court procedures).

A lot of critical literature concerning the development of digital dispute resolution, presented as a full alternative to the mechanisms of state justice⁶, is being produced in continental Europe. Indeed, the loss of physical proximity, as well as the potential loss of the guarantees related to court procedures are only a part of the negative externalities highlighted in scholarship.

In any case, the profound differences that still exist between national rules severely restrict the use of mediation in cross-border disputes, but, above all, prevent the efficient development of the

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⁴ M. GIACALONE, *Alternative dispute resolution e garanzia di accesso alla giustizia*, Naples, 2020, p. 23.

⁵ R. KOULU, *Law, Technology and Dispute Resolution*, Routledge, 2019, p. 88.

⁶ P. CORTÉS, *The Online Court: Filling the Gaps of the Civil Justice System?* in *Civil Justice Quarterly*, Vol. 36 n. 1, 2017, pp. 54-71; J. BARRET, *A History of Alternative Dispute Resolution: the Story of a Political, Social, and Cultural Movement*, San Francisco, 2004, pp. 182-214; G. DE PALO and E. PALO, M.B. TREVOR, *EU mediation Law and practice in Oxford University Press*, Oxford, 2015; C. ESPLUGES, L. MARQUIS, *New developments in Civil and Commercial Mediation*, Heidelberg/New York/Dordrecht/London, 2015.

amicable dispute settlement service as an alternative form of justice that complements the courts⁷. In this regard, it is to be noted that the development of mediation is not progressing in the European system at the same speed as in the non-European systems in which it originated, particularly in the common law world.

The reason for this process developing at different speeds may be summarised as follows. In non-EU countries, mediation arose and developed under the impetus of market requirements. Indeed, large companies in the manufacturing, financial and mass communications sectors have been quick to perceive the need for efficient and rapid dispute resolution mechanisms.

In continental law systems, on the contrary, the development of alternative remedies is, at least in appearance, slower and ill adapted to the needs not only of producers and large companies, but also to those of citizens and small entrepreneurs. This is possibly due to the fact that, in Europe, constitutional traditions and international treaties protecting human rights are all firmly grounded on the principles of the rule of law and the protection of fundamental rights⁸, among which access to justice⁹, which are allegedly impaired by the diffused recourse to ADR especially if administered online. For this reason, these systems have shown significant prudence with regard to such forms of dispute resolution.

Indeed, the debate is focused on finding a balance between the need for efficiency and simplification of dispute settlement mechanisms and the effective protection of fundamental rights and principles, such as access to justice and the effectiveness of the remedies provided in the system. The real issue for citizens and businesses is that of being able to have their rights safeguarded, whether by judicial means, by alternative means or by preventive means.

It is arguable, however, that access to justice¹⁰ does not necessarily mean access to the judicial process¹¹ and, with the aim of overcoming the issue related to the length of trials¹², the European Union has also placed emphasis on alternative means of dispute resolution, even online. In order to achieve this objective, alternative procedures must be improved and promoted.

In this regard, various initiatives have been developed in the European Union. First, the EU has proceeded issuing recommendations¹³, i.e., non-binding acts, which seek to enucleate the principles which shall inspire the composition of bodies that govern out-of-court settlement in consumer disputes: guarantees of independence of the decision-making body, which, if collegial, must be composed of an equal number of representatives of consumers and professionals; it must have proven capacity, experience and competence. Then, EU institutions have also approved binding acts¹⁴ to transform these principles in specific rules, especially in the sector of consumer disputes.

⁷ See also: C. MACHO GÓMEZ, *Origen y evolución de la mediación: el nacimiento del «movimiento ADR*, in Estados Unidos y su expansión a Europa, in *Anuario de derecho civil*, LX, v. II, n. 1, 2014; F. CUOMO ULLOA, *La conciliazione. Modelli di composizione dei conflitti*, Padova, 2008; M. CARRASCO, *Mediación y Sistemas Alternativos de resolución de Conflictos. Una visión Jurídica*, Reus/Madrid, 2009.

⁸ B. Z. TAMANAHA, *On the Rule of Law: History, Politics, Theory*, Cambridge University Press, 2004, p. 7.

⁹ Art. 47 of Eu Charter of Fundamental Rights expressly provides: “Everyone whose rights and freedoms guaranteed by the law of the Union are violated has the right to an effective remedy before a tribunal in compliance with the conditions laid down in this Article. Everyone is entitled to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial tribunal previously established by law. Everyone shall have the possibility of being advised, defended and represented”. Legal aid shall be made available to those who lack sufficient resources in so far as such aid is necessary to ensure effective access to justice.

¹⁰ Rule of law is meaningless unless there is access to justice. Access to justice is one of the constitutionally recognised human and fundamental rights. Access to justice means to reach justice easily by legally proceedings in appropriate time. Delivery of justice should be impartial and non-discriminatory, state taking all necessary steps to provide fair, transparent, effective, and accountable service that promote access to justice for all legal aid programs are a central component of strategies to enhance access to justice. M. CAPPELLETTI, *Access to justice and the Welfare State*, Alphen aan den Rijn-Bruxelles-Stuttgart-Firenze, 1981; A. GAMBARO, *La tutela degli interessi diffusi nel diritto comparato*, Milano, 1976.

¹¹ Access to judicial process is often used as a term for access to the formal institution of the legal system by those in search of a remedy either individuals in a particular civil or criminal case or collectively in a group of action or constitutional challenges. P. CALAMANDREI, *L’avenire dei diritti di libertà*, in *Opere giuridiche* (edited by M. CAPPELLETTI), vol. III, Napoli, 1968, pp. 183 ss; M. CAPPELLETTI e B. GARTH, vol. III; *Access to justice III: emerging issues and perspectives* (edited by), 1979; vol. IV, *Access to justice IV: the anthropological perspective* (edited by K. F. Koch), 1979.

¹² E.g., Small claims procedures or European Enforcement Orders Regulations.

¹³ Eu Commission Recommendation of 30 March 1998 on the principles applicable to the bodies responsible for out-of-court settlement of consumer disputes (98/257/EC); European Commission Recommendation 2001/310/EC on the principles for out-of-bodies involved in the consensual resolution of consumer disputes, OJ L 109. 19.04.01. p. 56-61.

¹⁴ Directive 2008/52/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on certain aspects of mediation in civil and commercial matters, OJ L 136, 24.5.2008, p. 3-8.

Available at <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008L0052&from=EN>.

From the EU Member States' perspective, out-of-court protection through ADR and ODR mechanisms still needs the implementation of key principles and organisational tools to fulfil the complementary function of alternative justice. In its efforts to promote alternative dispute resolution, the EU is attributing particular importance to various fundamental principles related to the settlement of disputes.

The first of them is transparency, which shall aim to ensure that the persons concerned receive the desired information on the limits of the body's jurisdiction - the procedure, the costs, the applicable law and the legal force of the decision. Indeed, if disputants decide to use a 'third party' to resolve their dispute, they must be sure that this third party is able to provide them with all the necessary information, precisely, on the body's competence, its ability to influence the fate of the dispute, the type of procedure that must be carried out to give rise to mediation, as well as the costs, the applicable law and the binding force of the decision¹⁵. In this sense, reference should be made to another of the aims set by the European Union: that of regulating the relationship between alternative means and ordinary justice and extrajudicial procedures which cannot be a complete substitute for the former. From this angle, it follows that the parties must be informed and must give their explicit consent to settle the dispute through out-of-court bodies and that the obligation contractually assumed to adhere to the out-of-court procedure cannot deprive - this is the most important consequence - the consumer of the right to sue. This consideration is related, on the one hand to the principle of freedom of contract, which imposes that recourse to ADR is always voluntary. On the other hand, the required express consent to ODR stems from the need to guarantee the fundamental right of access to justice, protected in our legal system by Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights and Article 47 of the European Union Charter of fundamental rights.

In addition, also in this matter, the right of the parties to be heard is a fundamental principle to be respected in all cases. Nevertheless, this inalienable criterion shall be balanced with the needs of online procedures, like the effectiveness of the procedure and the simplification.

Furthermore, in the parallelism between access to justice and access to ADR, there is the need that the principle of effectiveness of procedure of the alternative procedures shall be ensured by systems that guarantee consumers recourse to them, even without the obligation to have a legal representative.

Another element that must inspire the body wishing to identify the out of court settlement is legality. In fact, the decision may be taken based on legal rules or even according to equity¹⁶, as well as based on codes of conduct, if there is a standard of guarantees: there must be a level, albeit minimal, of "stakes". This "hard core" is represented by the inviolability of the mandatory provisions of the law¹⁷. In this area, too, it is essential to ensure the inviolability of mandatory provisions of the law protecting the consumer under the law of the state in which the body is constituted or in the state in which the consumer has his habitual residence.

In addition to the above, it is worth mentioning that, in October 1999, the well-known European Council that took place in Tampere defined new perspectives on justice within the European Union¹⁸. On that occasion, the European Council called for the simplification of judicial procedures in relation to small claims and for more work and studies in the field of alternative dispute resolution. Then, with the 2001 Recommendation¹⁹, the scope of application of these principles was extended to all out-of-court procedures which, whatever they are called, lead to the settlement of a dispute through the active intervention of a third party, whether they are solutions merely suggested to the parties or genuine decisions of a binding nature. This led to the creation of the European Extra-Judicial Dispute Resolution

¹⁵ G. BERNINI, *Report on neutrality, impartiality, and independence in International Commercial Arbitration. A Transnational Perspective*, edited by Tibor Várady, John J. Barceló III and Arthur T. von Mehren, Thomson-West, St. Paul, 2006.

¹⁶ In this case, equity must necessarily be subject to a legality check. As duly explained in P. PERLINGERI, *Equità ed ordinamento giuridico*, in *Rass. dir. civ.*, 2004, p. 1150.

¹⁷ Directive 2013/11/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2013 on alternative dispute resolution for consumer disputes and amending Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004 and Directive 2009/22/EC, OJ L 165, 18.6.2013, p. 63-79.

Available at <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:165:0063:0079:EN:PDF>.

¹⁸ Conclusions of Tampere European Council 15 and 16 October 1999, available here: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/summits/tam_en.htm

¹⁹ European Commission Recommendation 2001/310/EC on the principles for out-of-bodies involved in the consensual resolution of consumer disputes, OJ L 109, 19.04.01, p. 56-61. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32001H0310&qid=1401955449220&from=EN>.

Network²⁰, which resulted in an initial census of the out-of-court settlement bodies already operating in the various States. The objective of the European extra-judicial network is to enable consumers to direct themselves to a single contact point or clearing house in their own Member State to obtain information on the national systems in force in the other Member States and, in the case of cross-border disputes, to allow streamlined and simple access to a rapid legal means of out-of-court settlement of the dispute in the supplier country, through a national contact point, networked with the country from which the request originates²¹.

Therefore, it is possible to talk about a constituent phase of elaboration of a new European culture of mediation, which is welcome because it will lead to the definition of the indispensable guarantees to be observed in the participatory procedures through which, in a circular way, mediation is built, organised, implemented and, each with each iteration, develops and evolves.

In light of the above, this paper will try to address the state of art concerning the development of e-mediation in Europe in comparison with the (mainly common law) systems in which ADRs have emerged and developed. From this analysis, the reasons for the slower evolution of ADR and mediation have had in Europe should emerge.

2. Mediation: Concepts and controversial aspects. – Before investigating the relevant aspects of e-mediation, which we intend to carry out in the following sections, it is necessary to clarify some fundamental notions regarding the mechanism of mediation. Mediation²² is a structured process - however named or referred to - whereby two or more litigants to a dispute try by themselves, on a voluntary basis, to reach an agreement on the settlement of their dispute with the assistance of a mediator²³. This process may be initiated by the parties or suggested or ordered by a court or prescribed by the law of a Member State²⁴.

The recourse to mediation²⁵ is usually based on the will of the parties, who, in order to settle their dispute, decide to initiate, conduct and conclude a procedure aimed at finding a consensual settlement to be achieved through the conclusion of an agreement with the assistance of a mediator. Coherently with the voluntary character of mediation, the mediator must help the parties, conducting the proceedings in a way that is functional to the success of the attempt to reach an agreement (effectiveness), maintaining an equidistant attitude (impartiality) and with the necessary knowledge and skills (competence).

Mediation developed significantly since the second half of the last century, especially in Anglo-Saxon countries and in particular in the United States, where it was introduced from the 1960s/70s onwards with the aim of reducing disputes before the courts. The characteristics of mediation, i.e. low costs, the flexibility of the procedure and short timeframes, even compared to arbitration, have meant

²⁰ Council Resolution of 25 May 2000 on a community-wide network of national bodies for the extra-judicial settlement of consumer disputes [Official Journal C 155 of 06.06.2000]. The EEJ network was set up on 16 October 2001 by Commissioner David Byrne and the Belgian Presidency as a one-year pilot project. In the light of its success, the European Commission asked the Council of Ministers to extend this by one year. The Council approved the proposal and extended the pilot phase until the end of 2003. This network helped consumers to settle cross-border disputes with companies that provide defective goods or services, by guiding them towards alternative dispute resolution mechanisms (ADR).

²¹ The set of rules to be implemented through participatory processes of daily elaboration and experimentation of innovative solutions that meet the widest sharing can ensure both the full diffusion of the settlement service and the continuous improvement of the quality of ADR in all sectors and in every geographical area of application.

²² For a general overview, from an international perspective, of mediation as an out-of-court mechanism for the consensual resolution of disputes which, from the initial experience of the last century in the United States of America, has also spread to Europe, we would like to highlight some of the many published works: A. CASTAGNOLA, *La mediazione nelle controversie civili e commerciali*. Commentario al decreto legislativo 4 marzo 2010, n. 28 edited by A. CASTAGNOLA, F. DELFINI, Padova, 2010; AA.VV., *Quaderni di conciliazione* edited by C. PILIA, Cagliari, 2010; AA.VV., *La mediazione civile* edited by F. RUSCETTA, M. CARADONNA, F. NOVELLI, Milano, 2011; AA.VV., *Mediazione e conciliazione. Profili teorico-pratici*, edited by G. SCIANCALEPORE, S. SICA, Torino, 2010; AA.VV., *La mediazione civile e commerciale* edited by C. BESSO MARCHEIS, Torino, 2010.

²³ It includes mediation conducted by a judge who is not responsible for any judicial proceedings concerning the dispute in question.

²⁴ This is the definition of mediation given by Art. 13 of directive 2008/52/EC.

²⁵ On the European definitions of mediation and mediator cfr. C. ROGEL VIDE, *Los mediadores, sus obligaciones y su responsabilidad comentario crítico de los artículos 13, 16 y concordantes del anteproyecto de Ley de Mediación en asuntos civiles y mercantiles*, in *Revista general de legislación y jurisprudencia*, n. 2, 2010, pp. 309 ss.; R. SANTAGATA, *Mediazione, Mediatore e Conciliazione (Appunti su alcuni profili sostanziali del D.lvo 28/2010)*, in *Riv. dei dottori commercialisti*, 2, 2011, pp. 303 ss.; C. BESSO, *L'attuazione della direttiva europea n. 52 del 2008: uno sguardo comparativo*, in *Riv. Trim. dir. Proc. Civ.*, 2012, pp. 866 ss..

that (not only in the USA) mediation has become the most widespread alternative instrument for resolving internal commercial conflicts.

The recourse to mediation is today fostered both at the EU and at the international level.

EU Directive 2008/52/EC defines a 'mediator' as 'any third party who is asked to conduct mediation in an effective, impartial and competent manner, regardless of the denomination or profession of that third party in the Member State concerned and of the way that third party has been appointed or requested to conduct the mediation. This notion focuses on the position of third party that the mediator must assume in relation to the litigants of the dispute and on the function of conductor of the non-adjudicative procedure that is required of her, in order to assist the parties in seeking an agreement to settle the dispute²⁶. In this regard, the European legislator²⁷ expressly admits the compatibility of the definition with the different names or professions that are established for third parties in the individual national legislations of the Member States. Similarly, the compatibility with the various ways in which the mediator is appointed or invited to conduct mediation, according to national disciplines, is clarified²⁸. Indeed, in the abovementioned definition, the European legislator merely indicates how the mediator should conduct mediation: effectively, impartially and competently²⁹. This definition of 'mediation' is deliberately open-ended and tends to be pluralistic. Directive 2008/52/EC responds to the need to introduce for the first time a common, general and cross-cutting statute for mediation.

The same directive also specifies what cross-border disputes are by referring to the domicile or residence of the parties in different Member States³⁰, or to the different place where judicial proceedings or arbitration proceedings are initiated as a result of mediation. The European discipline of mediation, therefore, directly addresses disputes which, within the European Union, involve cross-border elements,

²⁶ In this sense, Directive 2008/52/EC (recital 11) expressly excludes from its scope out-of-court adjudication procedures (such as arbitration, expert witnesses, etc.) administered by persons or bodies that issue a formal decision or even a formal recommendation, whether formally binding or not, for the resolution of the dispute.

²⁷ See recital 10 of the Directive 2008/52 EC, in which EU legislator admits the compatibility of European Mediation with the various institutes and ways to start.

²⁸ G. VILLA-LUENGA in *Mediación en asuntos civiles y mercantiles, Comentarios a la Ley 5/2012* coordinated by L. GARCÍA VILLALUENGA, C. ROGEL VIDE, direct by C. FERNÁNDEZ CANALES, Reus, 2012, pp. 129 ss.; C. PILIA, *La tutela della riservatezza e il trattamento dei dati personali nella mediazione*, in *Quaderni di conciliazione* edited by C. PILIA, n. 3, 2013, Cagliari, pp. 183 ss.; A. BALTI, *La riservatezza del procedimento di mediazione delle controversie civili e commerciali dopo l'intervento della Corte costituzionale*, n. 6, 2017, pp. 61 ss.; P. LICCI, *Mediazione e conciliazione nel nuovo processo civile. Commento organico al d.lgs. 4 marzo 2010, n. 28, in materia di mediazione finalizzata alla conciliazione nelle controversie civili e commerciali*, edited by B. SASSANI, F. SANTAGATA, pp. 43 ss..

²⁹ Recital 18 of Directive 2008/52/EC, which refers to Commission Recommendation 2001/310/EC of 4 April 2001 on the principles applicable to out-of-court bodies involved in the collective resolution of consumer disputes (OJ L 109, 19.4.2001, p. 56). More specifically, the consumer source referred to expressly includes the principles of impartiality (II. A: "Impartiality must be guaranteed by ensuring that those in charge of the procedure: a) are appointed for a fixed period and cannot be relieved of their duties without just cause; b) do not have an apparent or actual conflict of interest with either party; c) provide information on their impartiality and competence to both parties prior to the commencement of the procedure") and effectiveness (II.C: "1. 2. The procedure shall be easily accessible and available to both parties, for example by electronic means, irrespective of where the parties are located. 3. The procedure shall be free of charge for consumers or, if there are costs, they shall be modest and proportionate to the amount in dispute. 4. The parties have access to the procedure without being obliged to engage a legal professional. However, the parties shall not be prevented from being represented or assisted by a third party at any stage of the procedure. 5. Once submitted, the dispute shall be dealt with as quickly as possible, commensurate with the nature of the dispute. Its progress shall be reviewed periodically by the body responsible for the procedure to ensure that it is dealt with expeditiously and in an appropriate manner. 6. The conduct of the parties shall be reviewed by the body responsible for the procedure to ensure that they are committed to seeking an appropriate, fair and timely resolution of the dispute. If the conduct of one party is unsatisfactory, both parties shall be informed in order to enable them to consider whether to continue the dispute settlement procedure. Moreover, the same principles, together with the principle of competence, have been taken up, developed and made binding as quality requirements through the subsequent EU framework for consumer ADR and ODR.

³⁰ On the European process of introducing a common discipline on mediation, which resulted in the approval of the fundamental Directive 2008/52/EC, among the numerous contributions published, see AA.VV., *ADR e mediazione*, edited by C. STICCHI DAMIANI, Torino, 2012; AA.VV., *Mediazione e conciliazione nelle controversie civili e commerciali*, Rimini, 2011, pp. 11 ss.; AA.VV., *Manuale della mediazione civile e commerciale. Il contributo del Notariato alla luce del d.lgs. n. 28/2010*, edited by M.L. CENNI, E. FABIANI, M. LEO, Naples, 2012; G. ZUCCONI GALLI FONSECA, "La mediazione civile nella prospettiva europea: note a prima lettura", in *Rivista trimestrale del diritto civile*, Milano, 2010, pp. 653 ss.; M. MICELI, *La direttiva CEE sulla Mediazione*, in *La mediazione nelle liti civili e commerciali*, Milano, 2011; S. LOPEZ VALLES, C.M. LOPEZ CARDENAS, *Aproximación a la regulación de la mediación en el derecho internacional privado y el derecho europeo*, in *Revista de Derecho Privado*, 2014; G. ROSSOLILLO, *I mezzi alternativi di risoluzione delle controversie (ADR) tra diritto comunitario e diritto internazionale*, in *Dir. UE*, 2008, pp. 349 ss.; A. DE LUCA, *La mediazione in Europa. Una questione di cultura e non di regole*, in *Riv. dir. civ.*, n. 6, 2013, pp. 1451 ss.; E. MINERVINI, *La proposta di direttiva comunitaria sulla conciliazione in materia civile e commerciale*, in *Contratto e impresa/Europa*, 2005, pp. 427 ss.; C. BESSO, *L'attuazione della direttiva europea n. 52 del 2008: uno sguardo comparativo*, in *Riv. trim. dir. proc. civ.*, n. 3, 2012, pp. 863 ss..

bi- or plurilateral, depending on the position of the conflicting parties. However, Member States are free to apply the provisions of the directive also to internal mediation proceedings.

European rules on mediation are of a general nature as they cover all disputes in civil and commercial matters³¹. The scope of application essentially embraces the entire private sphere of litigation as well as the public sphere, at least concerning disputes over transferable rights. In this sense, the directive expressly states that the discipline of mediation does not extend to fiscal, customs and administrative matters, nor to the liability of the State for acts or omissions in the exercise of public powers (*acta iure imperii*).

Because of these exclusions, therefore, Mediation Directive applies between parties, both public and private, whenever they have available rights which are the object of disputes that can be settled by an agreement.

This effort by the EU to develop mediation is to be located in a framework where traditionally most, if not all, European conflict resolution laws are focused on conflict resolution by the courts. While court proceedings are certainly a very valuable and important part of dispute resolution, the challenge is to build mechanisms that guide litigations to those solution methods that are best suited to solving the individual dispute.

Within this context, some countries, such as Austria, have opted for a high regulatory density on mediation. Arguments for this approach are consumer protection, the need for state promotion of mediation, legal certainty and the necessity to draw a line between mediation and professional legal services. The Austrian Civil Mediation Act (*Zivilrechts-Mediations-Gesetz*) contains detailed rules on a Mediation Advisory Council, a register of mediators, the rights and duties of registered mediators, the suspension of limitation periods and the training of mediators. In addition, a Regulation on the Training of Mediators (*Zivilrechts-Mediations-Ausbildungsverordnung*) lists in detail the knowledge and skills required for registered mediators.

In contrast, other countries, such as the Netherlands, prefer very few legislative interventions, in order to avoid suffocating the creativity and flexibility needed for a discipline that is still developing.

A third group of countries tries to solve the tension between the voluntariness of mediation and the abuse of freedom by some market actors through selected regulation. The first drafts of a new German Mediation Law (*Mediationsgesetz*) were heading in this direction. A comparative view reveals that the success of mediation is not clearly linked to a certain regulatory approach. Mediation has found success in jurisdictions with a less intensive regulatory approach (e.g. the Netherlands and the United Kingdom) as well as in jurisdictions with more intensive regulation (e.g. the USA).

Part of this challenge is to devise a structure that channels disputes to the best suited procedure at the entry stage, that is when the parties realise that bilateral negotiation will not lead to a solution. Also, the institutional conflict structures must make sure that disputes are transferred to another mechanism when the parties choose the "wrong door" at the entry stage. For example, legislatures must devise mechanisms to transfer a dispute to mediation, if the parties wrongly end up in court instead of in mediation.

A good example for integrating mediation institutionally can be found in the Netherlands³². Incoming cases there are screened by the judges as regards their suitability for mediation. In order to do this all judges have been trained to become familiar with mediation. The judges receive the necessary specific information for each case especially through a short questionnaire which the parties receive at the start of the civil court procedure.

On the international level, in order to facilitate the cross-border execution of mediation outcomes, the Singapore Convention was recently adopted, and its basic features should be outlined. The United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (henceforth UNCITRAL) has proposed, on an initiative formulated by the USA, the adoption of the Convention on Commercial Mediation opened for signature in Singapore on 7 August 2019³³. It allows agreements reached through a

³¹ Article 2 of Directive 2008/53 EC.

³² E. Katsh, *Online Dispute Resolution: Some Lesson from the E-Commerce Revolution* in *Northern Kentucky Law Review*, 2001, p. 810.

³³ At present, 53 countries have signed up to the Convention, including the USA, China and India, to name a few. On 12 March 2020, Qatar became the third country to ratify the Convention, after Singapore and Fiji. According to the Convention (Art. 14), on 12 September 2020 (i.e., 6 months after the deposit of the third instrument of ratification) the Convention will enter into force with respect to these first three countries. Currently, 6 countries have acceded.

mediation process concerning an international commercial dispute to be given enforceable effect in the acceding countries. The convention is applicable to any form of mediation, by whatever name, provided that the mediator helps the parties, without binding them to a decision. A "minimum" structure of mediation is not indicated, nor is the degree of involvement of the mediator. It is the centrality and freedom of the parties that is enhanced by this definition and that, along with its breadth, can lay the foundation for success. For the Convention to apply, the agreement must be reached as a result of international commercial mediation.

The Convention sets out the criteria for establishing its applicability and the grounds for exclusion. The agreement must be reached "in writing". Here the written form is interpreted very broadly, precisely because of the characteristics of international trade, the logistical difficulties and in view of the advanced technical means of communication that we have available today. As has been noted by many, international mediation could take place entirely by telephone, or on some online platform, and the agreement could result in an exchange of emails from the parties' accounts. So, the Convention of Singapore can be applied to e-mediation, as well³⁴. The Singapore Convention has been inspired by the great success reached by the 1958 New York Convention, which has made it possible to enforce in all contracting parties' arbitral awards issued in the territory of another state. In over 60 years, it has become the reference point for many legislations on international arbitration.

The adoption of an international treaty, modelled on the New York Convention, has therefore been promoted to ensure that agreements resulting from mediation are not merely contracts subject to a given legal system, but constitute genuine securities for enforcement in any State where this is necessary. Indeed, the success of international arbitration derives largely from the facilitation of the enforcement of arbitral awards provided by the New York Convention³⁵. Thus, it is evident that the absence of a similar instrument constitutes the main limitation to the use of mediation in international commercial relations.

3. *E-mediation: origin and current development.* – The recourse to mediation is recently facing a new phase, i.e. the development of e-mediation. To explore the historical profile and the up-to-date scenario concerning this form of dispute settlement, this paragraph will open with a brief discussion of the development of e-mediation within the wider context of ODR growth³⁶. E-mediation³⁷, indeed, became the main form of mediation during the Covid-19 pandemic when it became unsafe to meet in person.

Originally³⁸, there were several notable e-mediation projects undertaken during ODR's early, experimental phase³⁹ such as: (a) the "Online Ombuds project", which was a pilot ODR program established in 1996 by eBay⁴⁰, (b) The "Maryland Family Mediation Project", which was another early initiative funded by the National Center for Automated Information Research (NCAIR) in the United

³⁴ F. FRANZESE, *La Convenzione delle Nazioni Unite sull'esecutività degli accordi raggiunti in mediazione: un primo sguardo*, www.ilprocessocivile.it, Milano, 2020.

³⁵ G. ZARRA, *Una prima lettura della Convenzione di Singapore in tema di mediazione internazionale*, in *Diritto del Commercio Internazionale*, Fasc. 3/2021,764.

³⁶ M. CONLEY TYLER & J. BORNSTEIN, "Accreditation of Online Dispute Resolution Practitioners", in *Conflict Resolution Quarterly*, 2006, vol. 23, 3.

³⁷ N. EBNER writes in a chapter in *Online Dispute Resolution: Theory and Practice*, in *The Hague: Eleven International Publishing*, 2012, p. 357.

³⁸ In the late 1990s, various stakeholders, especially start-ups, began offering e-mediation services to organisations and the general public. The companies developed a roster of trained mediators whom they would assign to facilitate dispute resolution online, primarily through e-mail.

Online mediation services are now offered across the globe, both by service providers and increasingly by individual mediators. N. EBNER writes in a chapter in 'Online Dispute Resolution: Theory and Practice', Eleven International Publishing, 2012.

³⁹ Described by E. KATSH & J. RIFKIN & A. GAITENBY, *E-Commerce, E-Disputes, and E-Dispute Resolution: In the Shadow of eBay Law*, Ohio St. J., on *Disp. Resol.*, 2000, 15.

⁴⁰ In 1999, a pilot program for mediation of eBay disputes was conducted, an experiment which laid the groundwork for eBay's extensive employment of online negotiation and mediation which continues to this day. Over a two-week period, 225 buyers or sellers responded to an offer for free resolution of buyer-seller complaints. The complaints dealt with feedback, non-delivery of goods and other common eBay issues. Using e-mail for shuttle communication between the parties, due to parties' comfort with the medium, the mediator invited the other party to participate, asked to hear each side's stories, and proceeded to conduct a mediation process like face-to-face processes. See a sample transcript of one such process in E. KATSH & J. RIFKIN, *Online Dispute Resolution*, San Francisco, Jossey-Bass, 2001. 144 cases, or about 2/3 of the complaint cases, were mediated (others were unsuitable for mediation or resolved themselves). Out of these, 46% ended in agreement. See L. PONTE & T. CAVENAGH, *Cyberjustice: Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) for E-Commerce*, New Jersey, Prentice Hall, 2005.

States⁴¹, (c) the Cybertribunal project at the University of the Montreal School of Law, which later developed into “e-Resolution”, a commercial service provider practicing e-mediation as well as arbitration for domain name disputes⁴², and (d) “SquareTrade”, which picked up the eBay mediation project where the Online Ombuds left off, as a business venture⁴³.

After these initiatives, the sector developed offering e-mediation services to the general public. Among the early service providers were “Internet Neutral”⁴⁴, “e-Resolution” and “Online Resolution”. They dealt with a wide range of dispute types, including business-to-business and business-to-customers commercial disputes, workplace conflicts, and insurance issues. The number of cases that concretely went to mediation in this early phase was probably low, and indeed, many of the early mediation service providers did not remain active for more than a few years. However, other service providers took their place, and the number of initiatives increased⁴⁵.

Then, e-mediation has been provided all over the world, by both local and global providers.

In 2003, SquareTrade’s processes⁴⁶ had involved participants from over 120 countries and were conducted in five different languages. The geographical spread of service providers since then has resulted in e-mediation making headway in all regions of the world⁴⁷. Today companies often use online mediation to resolve high-volume, long-distance conflicts (such as disputes between eBay customers), the range of disputes being mediated online has expanded to include workplace and family conflicts involving people who live in the same area.

As with traditional mediation, disputants choose to engage in e-mediation on a voluntary basis and are usually assisted by a neutral third party. However, in e-mediation, the role of technology is often likened to a “fourth party” in the process⁴⁸, with the mediator considered as the third party. In this regard, it is to be noted that, initially, e-mediation was conducted primarily via e-mail and by telephone, but it has increasingly migrated to videoconferencing and online platforms, where real-time chats are sometimes used. Nowadays, e-mediation ranges from being completely automated, with technology guiding disputants through the process of sharing information and reaching agreement, to being led entirely by a trained mediator. When hiring a mediator, parties tend to look for someone who is trained in technology-aided mediation and has a strong understanding of e-mediation practices and procedures, including which online mediation software to use and when.

Practice shows that e-mediation may be an effective means of resolving disputes. It offers convenience, allowing parties to participate at a time that works for all parties, without the hassle and expense of travel. The procedure can be conducted at a slower pace than real-time conversations, as the process can be easily paused online. As such, e-mediation allows mediators and participants to carefully craft their responses and strategy rather than needing to react in the moment to statements.

⁴¹ In 1996, the Center for Law Practice Technology at the University of Maryland’s School of Law initiated a mediation project for family and health care disputes. This project, however, never quite got off the ground. See R.S. GRANAT, *Creating an Environment for Mediating Disputes On the Internet*, in *Center for Law Practice Technology at the University of Maryland School of Law. A working paper for the NCAIR Conference on On-Line Dispute Resolution*, Washington DC, 1996.

⁴² This commercial venture operated until 2002. See, for further information, E KATSH, J RIFKIN, A GAITENBY, *E-commerce, E-disputes, and E-dispute Resolution: In the Shadow of eBay Law*, in HeinOnline on Disp. Resol., Ohio St. J., 1999.

⁴³ Squaretrade offered a process in which parties to eBay feedback disputes began their contact with each other through automated negotiation, followed up by assisted negotiation. Only if agreement was not reached through these processes, were parties offered the use of a live mediator. Although most cases settled through the automated stages of the process, SquareTrade conducted many human-led mediations. See C. RULE, *Online Dispute Resolution for Business: B2B, E-Commerce, Consumer, Employment, Insurance, and Other Commercial Conflicts*, San Francisco, 2002.

⁴⁴ See B.L. BEAL, *Online Mediation: Has Its Time Come?*, Ohio St. Journal on Dispute Resolution, Ohio, 1999.

⁴⁵ See C. TYLER & J. BORNSTEIN, *Accreditation of Online Dispute Resolution Practitioners*, in *Conflict Resolution Quarterly*, 2006, p. 23; F.E.A. SANDER & L. ROZDEICZER, *Matching Cases and Dispute Resolution Procedures: Detailed Analysis Leading to a Mediation-Centered Approach*, in *Harv. Negot. L. Rev.*, 2006.

⁴⁶ See as specified above, in reference 44.

⁴⁷ According to Steve Abernethy, president of SquareTrade, during the period between 1999-mid-2003, 80% of the cases involving e-mediation resulted in agreement. While there are no firm numbers available on the volume of cases mediated by SquareTrade, there were certainly many thousands. Their operations continued until 2008, after which eBay integrated the feedback dispute resolution process into its in-house dispute resolution operations. eBay continues to implement hybrid processes beginning with automated negotiation and continuing on to optional human mediator intervention in the event of no agreement. See S. ABERNETHY, *The Square Trade Experience in Online and Offline Disputes*, in *Proceedings of the 2003 United Nations Forum on ODR*, 2003.

⁴⁸ J. PARLAMIS, N. EBNER, and L. MITCHELL, *Advancing Workplace Mediation Through Integration of Theory and Practice*, in Springer International Publishing, San Francisco, 2016.

At the same time, e-mediation may also shorten disputes by reducing scheduling difficulties. When conducted via e-mail or other text-based tools, mediation can level the playing field between disputants who tend to naturally dominate discussions and those who are more reserved⁴⁹.

Mediators may also behave differently when leading negotiations online than they do in person.

Disputants who engage in e-mediation need to remember that videoconferencing formats lack the full range of body language, facial expressions, and communication signals we have access to when we meet in person. E-mail, of course, is an even more “impoverished” communication medium, lacking visual and verbal cues. E-mediation can be prone to misunderstandings and may also lack the rapport and warmth of face-to-face talks. Because e-mediation can be dehumanising, parties may be tempted to abandon it entirely when frustrated.

More generally, it could be useful to consider the potential limitations of online formats up front so as to enable reference to them throughout the process. In e-mediation, parties may be less likely to blame each other when difficulties arise. In addition, it is wise to toggle between communication media throughout the process, choosing the format best suited to the task at hand. In the early stages, parties can take time to get to know each other and build rapport on video calls. Later in the process, they may want to exchange information or the details of offers via e-mail or pick up the phone when they need quick clarification⁵⁰.

4. *The development of consumer e-mediation within the EU.* – The EU is not extraneous to the process of development of e-mediation. Through a specific Regulation (EU), No 524/2013, on online dispute resolution for consumer disputes, the European legislator considered the digital dimension of the internal market, in order to facilitate access to easy, effective, quick and low-cost means of resolving disputes arising from the sale of goods or the provision of services online, especially for consumer cross-border transactions⁵¹.

The aims, scope and strategic guidelines of the European regulatory intervention are fully illustrated in the initial recitals of the abovementioned regulation⁵²: digitalisation of dispute settlement mechanisms, in fact, offers an easy, effective, quick and low-cost out-of-court solution for disputes arising from online transactions. Within Europe, all ADR entities and ODR entities, based on the principle of transparency, must make publicly available information on the ADR procedures that they manage, among other things, regarding the legal nature and the effects of the procedure⁵³. Furthermore, all ADR entities, based on the principle of transparency, must make available to the public the relevant information on the ADR procedures that they handle, inter alia, concerning the legal nature and the effects of the outcome, including their binding nature for the parties⁵⁴.

The insufficient availability of online mechanisms may entail disadvantages for consumers, hindering the completion of cross-border online transactions, creating an imbalance between traders and, consequently, hampering the general development of online commerce. EU institutions are confident⁵⁵ that the targeted discipline on mediation should also apply to online transactions, carried out at the national level, although consumers and traders carrying out cross-border transactions are the direct beneficiaries of the ODR platform.

⁴⁹ One study by Katalien Bollen and Martin Euwema of the University of Leuven, Belgium, subordinates mediating a dispute with a superior were significantly more satisfied with technology-supported mediation than with traditional face-to-face mediation.

⁵⁰ R. SAIJA, C. RIPEDI, D. MICALI, in AA.VV., *Procedimento di mediazione e accordo di conciliazione* edited by F. RENDE, in *Scienze e ricerche*, n. 32, 2016, pp. 47 ss.; R. TISCINI, *La mediazione civile e commerciale, Composizione della lite e processo nel d.lgs n. 23/2010 e nel D.M. nn. 180/2010 e 145/2011*, cit., pp. 189 ss.; F. CUOMO ULLOA, *La nuova mediazione*, Bologna, 2013, pp. 241 ss..

⁵¹ A. PÉREZ MORIONES, *La resolución de litigios en línea en materia de consumo: el reglamento (UE) n.º 524/2013, de 21 de Mayo de 2013*, in *Revista Doctrinal Aranzadi Civil-Mercantil*, n. 3, 2014, pp. 43 ss.; E. MINERVINI, *I sistemi di ODR*, in *Le online dispute resolution (ODR)* edited by E. Minervini, Naples, 2016, pp. 7 ss..

⁵² V. VIGORITI, *Superabili ambiguità. Le proposte europee in tema di ADR e ODR*, cit., pp. 315 s.; G. GIOIA, *Il nuovo “pacchetto” della Commissione europea sull’ADR*, in *Nuova giur. Comm.*, 2012, p. 697.

⁵³ E. ZUCCONI GALLI FONSECA, *Tutela arbitrale e tecnica del processo: la clausola compromissoria nei contratti di consumo*, in *Riv. trim. dir e proc civ.*, 2014, n. 3, pp. 997; M. MARINARO, *Food for thought for the harmonisation and rationalisation of ADR systems for consumer disputes*, in <https://www.judicium.it/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/M.-Marin角度1.pdf>, 2016.

⁵⁴ In the periodic reports that they must publish on their activities, ADR entities must specify, albeit with specific regard to the procedures under Article 2(2)(a) of Directive 2013/11/EU, the percentage of solutions proposed or imposed in favour of the trader and the consumer and those resolved by amicable settlement of the parties themselves.

⁵⁵ P. CORTES, *The new landscape of Consumer Redress: the European Directive on Consumer Alternative Dispute Resolution and the Regulation on Online Dispute Resolution*, in *The new regulatory framework for consumer dispute resolution*, pp. 29 ss..

On the other hand, the Regulation should not apply to disputes between consumers and traders arising from contracts for the sale or supply of services offline, nor to disputes between traders.

The European regulation⁵⁶ should be read in conjunction with the Directive 2013/11/EU, which requires Member States to ensure that all disputes between resident consumers and traders, established in the Union, arising from the sale of goods and the provision of services, can be submitted to an ADR entity.

Somebody in scholarship stated⁵⁷ that the ODR platform may be used not only for ADR procedures brought by consumers against traders but also for those brought by traders against consumers before ADR entities registered in the appropriate list referred to in Article 20(2) of Directive 2013/11/EU. Ensuring that all ADR entities are registered on the ODR platform should allow full coverage for online out-of-court resolution of disputes arising from online sales or service contracts.

Still on the level of sources, the ODR regulation for consumers does not affect the regulation on mediation, contained in Directive 2008/52/EU.

In light of the above, it can be inferred that the EU is slowly investing in e-mediation but that the current development of EU law in this area is still unsatisfactory. Despite the need for ODR, its growth has been slow when compared with traditional ADR, accounting for a very limited number of successful ODR providers. Presently, ODR is used for specific subject matters (e.g. the Uniform Domain Name Dispute Resolution Policy for domain names) and it operates in specific market places (e.g. PayPal for eBay). Some of their defining features are that they incorporate incentives for parties to participate and rely on non-legalistic self-enforcement mechanisms.

E-commerce is the most natural field for the application of ODR, in particular for settling complaints that are characterised for being cross-border, low value, high volume and occurring between Internet users.

In the EU system, the ADR directives and ODR regulation for consumer disputes are aimed at improving the retail market, by introducing a complex system of alternative options for resolution and internet solutions for out-of-court methods. The legislative changes will enable stabilisation of the EU's internal market, by providing consumers with an alternative to the common judiciary and traders, with a tool to avoid multi-annual processes⁵⁸.

Some European legal sources on ADR and ODR apply to consumer relationships only. More precisely, Directive 2013/11/EU applies to disputes between a consumer and a professional, identified in accordance with the corresponding well-established definitions, which are directly re-proposed, with a singularity worth mentioning. The definition of consumer, in fact, is susceptible to assume in the legislations of the Member States a broader scope of application which also includes the onerous purchase of goods and services, made by a natural person with a mixed purpose, consumer and professional, provided that the latter is not pre-eminent. From a subjective point of view, normally, only disputes brought by the consumer against the trader, and not vice versa, are subject to the discipline of ADR and ODR, unless the legislation of the Member States expressly allows this. Consequently, disputes concerning relations between professionals or between consumers and, in any case, between parties who do not possess the opposite subjective qualification are always excluded. From an objective point of view, consumer ADR and ODR expressly refer only to domestic and cross-border disputes arising from contractual obligations, linked to the sale of goods and the provision of services between an established professional and a consumer residing in the EU⁵⁹. Moreover, said Regulation further restricts its scope of application to the counter versus arising from the digital market. Therefore, consumer disputes arising from other contractual relationships, and in any case from non-contractual relationships, do not fall within the scope of application.

Finally, further limitations and exemptions from application are provided for by Directive 2013/11/EU, which, however, can be overcome in the implementing state laws. In these latter aspects,

⁵⁶ Regulation (EU) No 524/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2013 on online dispute resolution for consumer disputes and amending Regulation (EC) No 2006/2004 and Directive 2009/22/EC, OJ L 165, 18.6.2013, p. 1-12.

Available at <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:165:0001:0012:EN:PDF>.

⁵⁷ S. CASABONA, *Intermediazione digitale e composizione delle controversie: dall' alternative dispute resolution all' alien dispute resolution*, in *Il diritto dell'informazione e dell'informatica*, 2017, pp. 497 ss., 514 ss.

⁵⁸ K. Mania, *Online dispute resolution: the future of justice*, in *International Comparative Jurisprudence*, 2015, p. 76-86.

⁵⁹ See Regulation No. 524/2013 Art. 4(1)(a), Directive 2013/11/EU.

therefore, in the legislation of each Member State there could be further differences in the extension of the scope of application of ADR and ODR for consumers.

In summary, in order to delineate the area of overlap between the discipline of mediation in civil and commercial disputes and that of consumer ADR and ODR, one can use the term "consumer mediation" which has become common practice. With reference to the scope of application, finally, it must be underlined that while Directive 2008/52/EC is directly referable to cross-border disputes, although most Member States have extended it also to domestic disputes, Directive 2013/11/EU and Regulation No. 524/2013 cover both domestic and transnational disputes⁶⁰. This shows that consumer claims keep being pioneers compared with the more general mediation in civil and commercial matters, as happened in the beginning of the EU intervention in this area, when the non-binding act (recommendations of the end of 1990's) represented the basis of existing binding measures (directives and regulations here in examination)⁶¹.

5. E- mediation: the common law experience.

5.1 USA. – In the United States of America, the evolution of online mediation received a great deal of attention even before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic⁶², as testified by the Model Standards of Conduct for mediators by the American Bar Association ("ABA"), which highlighted the importance of the concepts of party autonomy and contractual self-determination as fundamental principles of the legal system and crucial steps towards the development of mediation⁶³.

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, online mediation was used by companies to resolve high-volume and long-distance disputes. For instance, singular instances of mediation conducted via remote communicational tools occurred back in the 1980s⁶⁴. Then, as already mentioned, eBay, a pioneer of consumer ODR, since the early 2000s began to allow its customers to resolve their disputes through the third-party dispute resolution provider "SquareTrade", which allows the users to resolve their dispute online through an external professional mediator⁶⁵. During the 2000s, indeed, scientific articles focusing on applying technology to mediation appeared in law (and particularly ADR) journals⁶⁶. Initial discussions on e-mediation ranged from conducting wholly online mediation processes to hybrid processes using online communication tools as an interactional mode distinct from primary face to face proceedings, to some application of online technologies to facilitate traditional face- to-face processes⁶⁷.

In the USA, the high volumes of low-value cross-border disputes, within marketplaces, like eBay⁶⁸ and Amazon were so out of sync with the court system that they required a new resolution process specifically built to resolve them⁶⁹. Technology companies pushed the creation and evolution of ODR because they needed to have a justice system for their users, because the existing justice system

⁶⁰ V. MIRRA, *Alternative Dispute Resolution systems find new vigour: the transposition of the ADR Directive and the introduction of the new "Arbitro per le Controversie Finanziarie*, in *Riv. dell'Arbitrato*, 2016, p. 693.

⁶¹ The possible domestic nature of mediation does not constitute a limitation in its application in consumer matters. G. ALPA, *Arbitration and ADR reforms in Italy*, in *Diritto del commercio internazionale*, 2017, p. 259.

⁶² A. CARREL & N. EBNER, *Mind the Gap: Bringing Technology to the Mediation Table*, in *Journal of Dispute Resolution*, 2019.

⁶³ Standard 1, American Bar Association & American Arbitration Association & Association for Conflict Resolution, Model Standards of Conduct (2005).

⁶⁴ D. ALLEN LARSON, *Technology Mediated Dispute Resolution (TMDR): Opportunities and Dangers*, in *University of Toledo Law Review*, 2020.

⁶⁵ eBay Services: Buying and Selling Tools: Dispute Resolution Overview, Pages.ebay.com (2020), <https://pages.ebay.com/services/buyandsell/disputeres.html> (last visited May 2, 2020).

⁶⁶ As recalled by a prominent mediator in the field of eBay disputes: Interview of Paul Eric Mason, International Counsel, Arbitrator and Mediator, Miami and Rio de Janeiro based, <https://www.paulemason.info/>, 2020.

⁶⁷ Numerous professional associations and dispute resolution providers have gathered resources helping their members or users navigate through online arbitration and/or mediation processes. E.g.: Navigating Disputes Arising from the Coronavirus (COVID-19) Crisis; Jamsadr.com (2020), <https://www.jamsadr.com/coronavirus/>;

Arbitration and Mediation in the Time of Coronavirus, Americanbar.org (2020), https://www.americanbar.org/groups/dispute_resolution/resources/resources-for-mediatingonline/arbitration-and-mediation-in-the-time-of-coronavirus/, 2020.

⁶⁸ C. RULE, *Making Peace on eBay: Resolving Disputes in the World's Largest Marketplace*, in *ACResolution Magazine*, 2008, <http://colinrule.com/writing/acr2008>.

⁶⁹ eBay, Facebook, Amazon, Airbnb and other massive platforms create e potential for other of market position. So, they may be considered hostile to the Rule of law principle. T. ENDICOTT, *The Rule of Law and Online dispute Resolution*, in *Online Dispute Resolution: virtud civica digital, democracia y derecho*, Madrid, 2017, p. 21 ss.

couldn't work for those cases. The private sector rapidly innovated around ODR in order to solve this problem.

Then, during the COVID-19 pandemic, social distancing and stay at home orders in most parts of the U.S.A. reinforced the interest in wholly integrated online mediation proceedings, based on more personalised technology designs attempting to make online meetings as effective and efficient as face-to-face ones⁷⁰. United States experienced a surge of demand and supply of online mediation venues during the pandemic, while this effort is primarily driven by conscious members of the mediator community, mediation and arbitration institutes, and professional organisations such as the International Council for Online Dispute Resolution (“ICODR”), the National Center for State Courts and the ABA⁷¹.

A significant focus has been put on improving the technological competence of mediators and data security, which could lead to the emergence of a more self-determined and tightly self-regulated ODR profession⁷².

As soon as the demand for online mediation increased, the issue of the technical competence of American mediators became crucial. At the beginning of March 2021, prominent national mediation service providers such as “JAMS” and the “CPR International Institute for Conflict Prevention & Resolution” started to launch training of their neutrals and advocates on topics of how to use professional online meeting platforms, such as “Zoom”, “LifeSize”, or other high-quality video conferencing systems⁷³. But also, smaller and more regional private mediation groups also provided necessary tools to deal with the increasing need for mediators and parties to conduct meetings online⁷⁴. Their unique video conferencing platform known as “iChat” which utilises Cisco’s WebEx communication platform, already successfully provided online mediation services for commercial and family matters a few years back, and therefore has some special edge during a period like this⁷⁵.

On the other hand, technology companies specialised in providing either video conferencing services or built-in online chatting functions such as “slack.com”, “discord.com”, “rocket.chat” and “trokt.com” have caught the attention of the sector⁷⁶. Some of these platforms started to aggressively promote their services at a discounted price, hoping to gain more active users during the pandemic who stick with their services for a longer-term.

These platforms are currently not regulated and hence, do not have a judicial enforcement mechanism. Therefore, the outcome of the private ODR process is often imposed by a *community approach* (since the success of the Private ODR system depends on the participants, feedback loops, and other related methods that help in improving the process). In cases where the outcome is not enforced, a refund is provided. The connection between the participants’ trust in the system—including the ability to provide feedback and resolve disputes—and the willingness to undertake commercial activities online is connected for both Public and Private groups.

Examples of private ODR providers include the e-bay dispute resolution center, the Paypal dispute center, and Amazon ODR. In the USA, however, public ODR providers also exist and they are usually compared to a virtual courthouse. This is because public ODR platforms follow the same rules and regulations as traditional courthouses and are similarly monitored. Therefore, public ODR providers are more robust and capable than corresponding Private ODR providers as they handle a smaller variety of issues in courthouse settings with modifications for the use of technology.

⁷⁰Guideline B-8 on Alternative Dispute Resolution and Online Dispute Resolution, November 2021, https://www.americanbar.org/groups/legal_aid_indigent_defense/resource_center_for_access_to_justice/standards-and-policy/

⁷¹ The Demand for Online Mediation Spikes During COVID-19 Coronavirus Outbreak, Cbs19news.com (2020), <https://www.cbs19news.com/story/41874167/the-demand-for-online-mediation-spikes-during-covid-19>(last visited May 2, 2020).

⁷² Online Dispute Resolution Technical Interface Standards (Working Draft 3). National Center for State Courts (USA).

⁷³ Course: Understanding the Basics of Online Mediation, at 9, Online Mediator Resources, Google Docs (2020), https://docs.google.com/document/d/IQMGegpeb3Z_trEe4kKBXUYIrvRB8aV3rQdRZZSaksc/edit?usp=sharing.

⁷⁴ For example, M. BRICKMAN, founder of the Florida mediation group iMediate Inc., stated in an interview that “in responding to the spread of the COVID-19, iMediate Inc. promises to work with our clients to address this growing public health crisis in a smart, strategic, and serious manner”.

⁷⁵ E. E. GREENBERG, N. EBNER, *What Dinosaurs Can Teach Lawyers About How to Avoid Extinction in the ODR Evolution*, in *St. John's Legal Studies Research*, Paper No. 19-0004, 2020.

⁷⁶ See A. MAMO, *Three Ways of Looking at Dispute Resolution*, in *Wake Forest Law Review*, 2020, available at https://papers.ssm.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3386840, at p. 40.

5.2 *Canada*. – Canada is well known for the development of the online dispute resolution process. The Canadian Civil Resolution (CRT)⁷⁷ is Canada’s first online tribunal for resolving strata and other types of disputes including small claims disputes of up to \$5,000 (including specific types of traffic injury disputes). It was primarily developed in 2011, as an alternative to the existing traditional courts in British Columbia, Canada⁷⁸.

The CRT offers new ways to resolve disputes and legal issues in a timely and cost-effective manner. It encourages a collaborative, problem-solving approach to dispute resolution, rather than the traditional courtroom model. It also aims to provide timely access to justice, built around life needs. It does this by providing legal information, self-help tools, and dispute resolution services to help solve problems as early as possible⁷⁹. In order to reach this goal, it is available 24 hours a day, seven days a week, from a computer or mobile device that has an internet connection. The interaction with the other participant(s) and/or the CRT can be done when it is convenient for each litigant. CRT services are also available by phone⁸⁰. Direct and active participation will help reach a resolution with the other participant(s). The CRT decides, instead of the parties, that only one of the participants cannot agree on their own solution⁸¹.

The CRT can resolve a wide variety of disputes between strata owners and strata corporations, such as: non-payment of monthly strata fees or fines; unfair actions by the strata corporation or by people owning more than half of the strata lots in a complex; unfair, arbitrary or non-enforcement of strata bylaws (such as noise, pets, parking, rentals); issues of financial responsibility for repairs and the choice of bids for services; irregularities in the conduct of meetings, voting, minutes or other matters; interpretation of the legislation, regulations or bylaws; issues regarding the common property.

5.3 *Australia*. – For some years, the Federal Court of Australia has provided a limited range of electronic services, including videoconferencing, e-lodgement (for electronic filing) and an e-Court with limited judicial capacity⁸². Most courts and tribunals in Australia now offer electronic lodgement facilities. “NSW” has an online registry for its courts, enabling online lodgement of matters and, in some courts, online management of procedural aspects of cases⁸³.

Anyway, in this country, ODR has not reached the level of support and development that might have been anticipated from a nation with noteworthy geographic isolation and whose population maintains a reputation for ready up-take of new technologies.

More advanced is the scenario concerning family matters. In this regard, Australia offers a national Family Relationship Advice Line⁸⁴ and an associated Telephone Dispute Resolution Service. Additional services include a range of technologies that enable families to participate in online dispute resolution, where such services have been assessed as suitable in any case⁸⁵.

A service to help separating families resolve their family law disputes, The Family Dispute Resolution Service (formerly known as the Family Mediation Service) can provide information, counselling, dispute resolution and group programs to help couples who are separating to resolve their

⁷⁷ See Civil Resolution Tribunals <<https://civilresolutionbc.ca/how-the-crt-works/getting-started/strata-solution-explorer>> accessed 29 April 2021.

⁷⁸ A. H. RAYMOND and S. J. SHACKELFORD, *Technology, ethics, and access to justice: Should an algorithm be deciding your case?*, in *Journal of International Law* 485, 505, Michigan, 2014.

⁷⁹ See M. GIACALONE, S. S. SALEHI, *Online Dispute Resolution: The Perspective of Service Providers*, chapter of the book *Algorithmic Conflict Resolution*, edited by F. Romeo, M. Dall’Aglia and M. Giacalone, Torino, 2019. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3782370>.

⁸⁰ In 2019, Laboratoire de cyberjustice launched a program to introduce ODR in workplace disputes in Canada: www.cyberjustice.ca.

⁸¹ Learn more about the Civil Resolution Tribunal at the CRT website. The CRT makes the internet, rather than courthouses, the place where citizens access justice.

⁸² The first developments in using decision-support systems in the context of dispute resolution in Australia were through the efforts of Zeleznikow and Stranieri within their ‘Split-Up’ project.

⁸³ See E. BELLUCCI and J. ZELEZNIKOW, *Developing Negotiation Decision Support Systems That Support Mediators: A Case Study of the Family-Winner System* in *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Law*, 2006.

⁸⁴ See supra 59.

⁸⁵ These have arisen as a result of a Relationships Australia report published by AGD, “Development and Evaluation of Online Family Dispute Resolution Capabilities”, 2011.

family law disputes. These disputes may include conflicts over childcare, child support, financial arrangements and property settlement⁸⁶.

Family Dispute Resolution aims to help separating couples reach agreements that are in the best interest of their children. It also encourages separating couples to parent cooperatively.

5.4 *United Kingdom*. – In the last six years, the development of e-mediation in United Kingdom is easily shown through the analysis of the law-making process. In its 2015 report, the ODR Advisory Group of the Civil Justice Council recommended that ODR be made available for the resolution of low value civil claims⁸⁷. Their report suggested the establishment of Her Majesty's Online Court (HMOC)⁸⁸ and included a recommendation that cases be decided online by judges, through instruments including electronic interaction with parties and early intervention by online facilitators. In this report it was observed that, being cheaper and more user friendly than traditional Courts, such an approach would increase access to justice and that the new online court would lead to substantial cost savings in the legal system⁸⁹.

In July 2016, in his own Civil Courts Structure Review, Lord Justice Briggs endorsed the ODR Advisory Group's recommendations about HMOC, and, in his acceptance of Lord Justice Briggs' Report, the Lord Chief Justice noted that HMOC was already listed in the reform program of the Civil Courts of England and Wales⁹⁰.

Her Majesty's Courts and Tribunals Service require claimants and defendants to use an online portal to commence and to conduct proceedings⁹¹. This is, in fact, the regular operation of the English County Courts, exercising the jurisdiction they have long held to decide claims in debt. Money Claim Online does more than just use technology to make the judicial process less clumsy; the Court has authority to refer the case to a mediator. But if mediation is unsuccessful, the parties end up in front of a judge, in a courthouse, within the judicial paradigm of dispute resolution according to law. And here an important aspect concerning the relationship between ODR and the rule of law shall be noted: to the extent that ODR makes court proceedings quicker, cheaper, more transparent and less stressful, it is a positive and potentially highly significant advance in the rule of law. It is a step toward more effective resolution of disputes according to law⁹².

6. *The reason for European traditional scepticism on e-mediation and the lesson to be learned from common law systems*. – The overview given in the previous paragraphs has highlighted the different degree of development of e-mediation in common law systems and in the European Union.

⁸⁶Learn more about the Family Dispute Resolution process. Parenting Plans (pdf) or agreements are used to assist in this process. For more information about the Family Dispute Resolution Service, find Relationships Australia office.

⁸⁷ In February of 2015, the UK's ODR Advisory Group (ODRAG), chaired by Prof. Richard Susskind, proposed to establish a three-stage internet-based court system in the UK, known as Her Majesty's Online Court (HMOC) (see the 'Online Dispute Resolution for Low Value Civil Claims' report). According to their report, the first stage would be dedicated to the evaluation of the issues brought forth by parties, helping them avoid legal conflict and assisting them to resolve difficulties before they develop into substantial legal problems. However, if disputes cannot be resolved during this first stage, they shall be moved on to the second stage. Online facilitators would help the parties find a solution to their dispute during this stage. This second stage may involve any kind of 'Alternative Dispute Resolution' (ADR) and may also possibly involve the use of artificial intelligence. Judges shall only intervene during the third stage if no agreement has been reached between the parties over the course of the second stage. Judges shall resolve disputes between parties electronically, following a structured online pleading procedure.

⁸⁸ For further information, see: <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/hm-revenue-customs>.

⁸⁹ The proposal to create online courts for England and Wales has been well documented in the Civil Justice Council Advisory Group Report on online dispute resolution (ODR), Lord Justice Briggs' Reports on the Civil Courts Structure Review and more recently by a joint paper published by the Ministry of Justice, the Lord Chancellor, the Lord Chief Justice and the Senior President of Tribunals.

⁹⁰ Lord Justice Briggs's final report in his review of the future of the civil courts structure was published last week. Key recommendations relevant to commercial parties include: establishing an Online Court, initially for money claims up to £25,000; a substantial increase in the minimum claim value threshold for commencing claims in the High Court – initially to £250,000 and subsequently to £500,000; transferring some of judges' more routine and non-contentious work to case officers, under judicial training and supervision; there should not be a move to a unified civil court (ie combining the High Court and County Court) but the time has come for a debate about the future of the High Court Divisions (beyond the scope of this review); the County Court should become the single default court for the enforcement of judgments and orders of all the civil courts, with enforcement procedures to be unified and digitised.

⁹¹ <https://www.moneyclaim.gov.uk/web/mcol/welcome>.

⁹² J. RAZ, *The rule of law and its virtue*, in *The Authority of Law*, in Oxford University Press, 2009, p. 214-218.

Private dispute resolution, enriched with the application of technology, is more developed in non-European countries, while within the EU the spread of the institution is slower.

What are the reasons for these divergences?

It is arguable that, apart from the different cultural backgrounds (common law systems tend more and more to valorise party autonomy in all fields), these divergences are mainly due to the different balance that the various systems of law find between the need to safeguard party autonomy in the regulation of commerce and the willingness to ensure the respect for the procedural guarantees related to the judicial process.

As is known, e-mediation is subject to rules comparable to those of ordinary justice, but the procedure and the decision are private and their publicity is limited to the parties. Thus, what e-mediation offers, which is different from state court systems, is a specialised mediation system and, most importantly, confidentiality. This means that commercially sensitive information is not in the public domain and decisions do not constitute precedent and do not contribute to the development of the rule of law. One of the main reasons why traders prefer e-mediation to litigation is exactly that the former is private and confidential in nature. As a result, high-value or sensitive business information does not become public, as can happen in litigation. This confidentiality also prevents the outcome of any dispute from becoming public and setting a precedent that can be used by other claimants who may have a similar claim.

Especially in extra-EU systems (e.g. U.S.A. and Canada) those who promote mediation generally express a distrust of the judicial process and assume that compromise is always preferable to a public judicial decision on the merits⁹³. Instead, in European civil law systems the development of e-mediation goes with the extension to this mechanism of the guarantees of the rule of law and of due process.

Beyond the benefit to private parties engaged in mediation, we should try to understand what the impact of mass privatisation of justice is and to what extent EU legal systems are ready to renounce significant control of dispute settlement mechanisms (even more than in international arbitration, considering that enforcement of mediation agreements will usually be spontaneous). This is to be verified especially in relation to certain elements of the rule of law⁹⁴, relative to the public value of the trial and the judicial decision, and to the loss of precedent, something that is nowadays perceived as a crucial element for the development of legal systems not only in the common law world⁹⁵ (where, as we have seen, there is a tendency to let the will of the parties prevail in any case).

A meaningful definition of the concept of “rule of law” was formulated by Tom Bingham⁹⁶, who considers it as “the condition in which every person and authority within the state, whether a public or private entity, is bound by the law and benefits from the protections of the law, publicly administered by the Courts”. Bingham identifies eight elements to define rule of law: the law must be accessible; questions of law must be decided through the law and not through discretion; equality before the law; power must be exercised according to law, fairly and reasonably; human rights must be protected; disputes must be resolved within a reasonable time and proceedings must not be excessively costly; the principle of fair trial must be guaranteed; the state must act in accordance with its national and international obligations.

From a European perspective, art. 2 TEU⁹⁷ includes the rule of law among the fundamental principles of the European Union. The concept of rule of law is mentioned in national and international legislation, but at the same time it is poorly defined. Moreover, the rule of law appears in the Statute of the Council of Europe and the European Convention on Human Rights, as well as in the Universal

⁹³ M. GALANTER, *The Vanishing Trial: an Examination of trials and related matters in Federal and State Courts*, in *Journal of Empirical Legal Studies*, 2004.

⁹⁴ The rule of law is almost universally supported at the national and international level. The extraordinary support for the rule of law in theory, however, is possible only because of widely divergent views of what it means in practice. Disparate national traditions posed few problems while operating in parallel, but efforts to promote the rule of law through international organizations have necessitated a reassessment of this pluralism.

⁹⁵ J. RESNIK, *Trial as Error, Jurisdiction as Injury: Transforming the Meaning of Article III*, in *Harvard Law Review* 113, 2000.

⁹⁶ T. BINGHAM, *The rule of law*, London, 2011; S. CHESTERMAN, *Rule of law*, in *The Max Planck Encyclopedias of International Law*, 07/2007.

⁹⁷ Art 2 TEU: “The Union is founded on the values of respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities. These values are common to the Member States in a society in which pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men prevail”.

Declaration of Human Rights, but none of these documents defines what is meant by the rule of law. The international body that has gone into greater detail in identifying this concept is the OSCE⁹⁸, which has adopted documents specifying the actions to be taken to strengthen the rule of law in the member states of the organization.

The public function of civil courts is to provide authoritative statements about what the law is, who has rights, and how those rights are to be vindicated. The norms and behaviours described in the law radiate out from the public statutes in courts and influence the behaviour of citizens in everyday interactions. These are essential elements of the public value of the judiciary.

Therefore, for civil justice to fulfil its public role, the publication of decisions is crucial. It has been argued that the ability of litigants to present reasoned arguments to an impartial third party is the essence of adversarial decision-making, and this in turn is the manifestation of the rule of law⁹⁹.

Publicity is expressed through the requirements of openness, knowledge, and accessibility, which are fundamental characteristics of the rule of law. Legal rules should be known and their application public. In privatising significant segments of the judicial function, one risks "systematically and consciously trampling on the key role of the protection of the rule of law"¹⁰⁰.

The civil justice system serves both individual and collective interests. Indeed, the private and the public are inextricably linked. In addition, private litigation can benefit the public system, not only by creating benchmarks that promote dispute resolution, but also by convincing potential infringers that the violation of rights is likely to be unprofitable¹⁰¹.

Relatedly, as we have seen - and this is very important, not only in common law systems -, private justice leads to the loss of precedent. We all know how decision-making in the courts plays a vitally important role. It enables the law to develop in the light of reasoned arguments, which is itself refined and tested before a number of tiers of the judiciary. It enables public scrutiny of the law as it develops. This means that those parts of society that have a direct interest in the decision and the principle it articulates may control it and subject it to public debate. On this basis, an issue can be brought back to the courts or to parliaments if necessary. Precedent ensures, as a necessary underpinning to public scrutiny, that the law's development is not hidden from view¹⁰².

It is inevitable that increasing privatization could lead to fewer precedents, which would adversely affect the goal of legal certainty. Unclear law can lead to uncertainty and risk aversion in the commercial world so that economic opportunities are not optimised. Moreover, where there is uncertainty, there is fertile ground for escalating litigation. Instead of indiscriminately "chasing away" cases, perhaps we should ask what cases should be streamlined in court and how access to them should be facilitated¹⁰³.

The increased prevalence of online mediation is likely to lead to a loss of established guidelines, resulting in unnecessary further conflict. This is an issue that still requires investigation.

First, the lack of precedent - as we have seen - is relevant to the foundation of dispute resolution. Private models of dispute resolution produce decisions that do not constitute judicial precedent, as state court decisions do. This is a matter of continuous self-renewal of law and social values. Indeed, it is difficult to ensure equality before the law if the procedures and their outcomes are not public and do not contribute to the renewal of the rules (in common law systems) and to the updating of their interpretation (in civil law systems).

On the other hand, however, precedents may be found when decisions made in private dispute resolution transit through the courts to access enforcement.

Not to mention that in a system highly characterised by technological innovation, it might be easy to create a database containing the results of e-mediation (amounts awarded, type of agreements reached), while keeping the parties involved and the causes of the dispute confidential. This would

⁹⁸ OSCE Ministerial Council, Decision No. 7/08 on further strengthening the rule of law in the OSCE area, 08/12/2008.

⁹⁹ J. GRUIN, *The rule of law, adjudication and hard cases: the effect of alternative dispute resolution on the doctrine of precedent*, in *Australasian Dispute Resolution Journal*, 2008.

¹⁰⁰ W. TWINING, *Theories of Litigation, Procedure and dispute settlement*, in *Dispute Resolution Civil Justice and Its Alternatives*, Vol. 56, No. 3, 1993, pp. 384-385.

¹⁰¹ A.W. ALSCHULER, *Mediation with a mugger: the shortage of adjudicative services and the need for two-tier trial system in civil cases*, in *Harvard Law Review*, p. 1808.

¹⁰² The Right Hon. The Lord Thomas of Cwmgiedd, Lord Chief Justice of England and Wales, "Developing commercial law through the courts: rebalancing the relationship between the courts and arbitration", The Bailii Lecture, 2016.

¹⁰³ T. BINGHAM T., *The rule of law*, England, 2011.

make it possible to increase legal certainty also for those who resort to online mediation, also making it possible to enhance the predictive character of the outcomes of consensual procedures.

It must also be kept in mind that technological change creates a mass of cases, which is an undesirable contingency for a legal system operating primarily through the state court. The reference applies, for example, to “bagatelle” cases, which typically arise from e-commerce and in which legal fees are likely to exceed the value of the litigation.

When these disputes become part of the cross-border context, the complexity of litigation increases. Deciding which court has jurisdiction also becomes challenging and time-consuming, and as a result, going to public courts may not actually be a viable option. Despite the apparent conflict between the principles of state jurisdiction, due process and protection of the individual in cross-border consumer cases, there is no doubt that e-mediation, as well as other remote ADRs, may be the best way to ensure effective access to justice in respect of those cases. The practice of non-European systems, in which online mediation has been widespread for a longer time, shows that the solution outside the courts has undoubted advantages in terms of costs and time of decision.

Therefore, it seems desirable to provide and improve the regulatory environment for ODR and private enforcement. This is a daunting task. Examining the regulation of private enforcement leads one into a minefield, as the question of exporting due process to private dispute resolution turns out to be a question of the legitimacy of any dispute resolution system. There is no need to question what it takes to have a good dispute resolution process enhanced by technology, but one must combine the principle of due process with that of bargaining autonomy, which is the foundation of private dispute resolution. Combining parties’ autonomy and State regulation is also necessary in the field of cross border execution of out-of-court settlements. In order to achieve stable economic growth, an open economic system is desirable, and it is therefore a priority for States to set up instruments that can support international trade activities. One of these instruments is the attribution of enforceability to international agreements reached in mediation.

The lack of confidence in some judicial systems, which makes the resolution of a dispute perceived as very difficult and uncertain, discourages economic operators from undertaking commercial activities in some countries. Therefore, mediation, if the conditions are created for its effective and efficient use at the international level, is an important tool to support the development of cross-border trade relations and, consequently, global economic development. Both mediation and e-mediation are expected to be increasingly used in Europe as well, both because of their low costs and because of the proper characteristics of this tool, which in many situations make it preferable to litigation.

For all the above reasons, there is a divergence between the development of e-mediation in non-European systems and in continental ones: the EU, precisely in view of the spread of the institute, has taken care to perfect the legislative and regulatory framework.

It is only by extending the principles of the rule of law and access to justice to ODR that private dispute resolution mechanisms, especially when favoured by technology, can meet with the trust of States, citizens and commercial operators¹⁰⁴.

However, trying to be realistic, even if ODR will prove to be successful, it will never completely replace litigation.

Ms. Hart, one of Canada's leading mediators, arbitrators and dispute process designers seems to think that the main reason for not choosing ODR mechanisms to solve e-disputes is exactly because ODR is voluntary and ODR solutions do not create precedents¹⁰⁵. E-disputes, like any other dispute, involve people, and people will always choose those mechanisms for resolving their dispute that they feel best serve their interests¹⁰⁶. She is convinced that in a new field, like e-commerce, people initially feel a strong need for a public precedent that can serve as a road mark for others. The fact that ODR is private and contractual means that it is not possible to achieve precedents through ODR nor is it possible

¹⁰⁴ Now there are numerous cases of domain name disputes in many legal systems being brought to the ordinary courts. domain name disputes can be dealt with quite success fully by arbitration, be it offline or online. This is yet only possible for domain name disputes concerning top-level domain names like .com, .org, .net. When registering such a domain name the holder agrees to be bound by the ICANN rules, that include arbitration rules. The same would be true for the choice of mediation to solve these kinds of disputes. So far parties do not seem to choose (online) alternative dispute resolution to solve their dispute.

¹⁰⁵ M. WILIKENS, A. VAHRENWALD, P. MORRIS, *Out-of-court dispute settlements systems for e-commerce. Report of an exploratory study*, 2000.

¹⁰⁶ M. GIACALONE, *alternative dispute resolution e garanzia di accesso alla giustizia*, Naples, 2020.

to force parties to participate in an ODR procedure. Ms. Hart mentions that even if there is ODR awareness and acceptance, it may not always be in the best interest of everyone to choose to participate. Sometimes it may be to someone's advantage to delay resolution¹⁰⁷.

The fact that ODR is voluntary means parties cannot be forced to participate. This may be a reason for the other party to opt for litigation.

For all these reasons it seems highly unlikely that ODR will ever come to replace the courts¹⁰⁸. This is true especially in European countries and civil law systems, clearly inspired by the rule of law and due process principles. E-mediation will always be an alternative to courts and, in all likelihood, it will become more important than it is now for reasons of speed, cost-efficiency and cross-border issues.

The very fact that ADR/ODR are private and contractual, which at first may be an obstacle, could in many cases become more of an advantage than a problem, because it also means there will be no publicity if you should be found to be in the wrong. However, ODR and its online counterparts will remain just what they are by nature: an alternative way of dispute resolution, be it online or offline.

Ultimately, the answer to all these new challenges stays in the relationship between private dispute resolution and state regulation¹⁰⁹. It is desirable that ODR be completely in accordance with the rule of law, especially providing resolution of disputes that cannot effectively be resolved through in-court dispute resolution. If ODR is not left completely in the hands of large market players, especially those operating in the field of distance selling, the main pathologies of traditional ODR, especially the ones antithetical to the principle of the rule of law, can be avoided: anarchy and the arbitrary exercise of power.

If the intervention of the legal system, however, manages to avoid these risks, ODR is not necessarily contrary to the rule of law and is intended to represent a huge advance in the perspective of the rule of law. In fact, as mentioned above, ODR succeeds in ensuring access to justice with respect to small cases that could not be conveniently handled in court. Hence, the Singapore Convention¹¹⁰, which aims to facilitate the cross-border enforcement of mediated solutions, should therefore be signed, endorsed by the EU and made more operational. Indeed, the objectives pursued by the Convention in part coincide with those of the path already undertaken by the European Union to promote the spread of mediation within it. Indeed, this Convention is a promising new international instrument aimed at facilitating the settlement of international commercial disputes by making enforceable international mediated settlement agreements, a significant feature previously assigned only to arbitral awards and some court judgments¹¹¹. With an encouraging initial appeal (53 signatory states and 6 ratifying states), the Singapore Convention is an important step towards promoting mediation on a global scale. Its actual impact, however, remains to be seen.

7. Conclusion. – The analysis carried out on the main legal practices on e-mediation shows a rapidly evolving legal framework which, despite being recently enacted - in fact, in Europe it dates back

¹⁰⁷ J. BEDAUX and R. HERMANS, *Arbitrageprocedure loont bij domeinnaamgeschillen*, in: 'De Automatiseringsgids', 23 June 2000, nr. 25, p. 17;

¹⁰⁸ C. HART, *Online Dispute Resolution and Avoidance In Electronic Commerce*, an article submitted for the *Uniform Law Conference of Canada*, august 1999, located at <http://www.law.ualberta.ca/alri/ulc/current/hart.htm>

¹⁰⁹ O. POLLICINO, M. BASSINI, *The Law of Internet between Globalisation and Localisation*, in M. MADURO, K. TUORI & S. SANKARI (eds), in *Transnational Law. Rethinking European Law and Legal Thinking*, in Cambridge University Press, 2014, p. 361.

¹¹⁰ Although it has not been formally clarified whose competence it is to sign, whether it is the EU or the individual member states. The solution to this question depends on the political will expressed by the states in the EU Council. Indeed, Article 12 of the Singapore Convention provides for the possibility of accession by "a regional economic integration organisation" in addition to its member states that are already signatories. Therefore, at least on a formal level, it would be admissible for the Convention to be signed both by individual member states and by the EU itself. It is singular to note, among other things, that the EU itself, in its Resolution of 12 September 2017, states that further measures need to be taken to ensure the enforceability of foreign mediation agreements in a swift and accessible manner. This is why it is to be hoped that the issue of competence to conclude does not deprive Europe of a means that could help, not only to develop "harmonious economic relations", as stated in the preamble of the Convention, but also to concretely support economic growth by safeguarding trade relations.

This is a fundamental objective, especially in the event of extraordinary and unforeseeable events, such as the covid19, which it is feared may occur with some frequency in the near future and which make it necessary to renegotiate contractual terms or negotiate the application of any force majeure clauses, which are mainly present in international trade contracts.

¹¹¹ Consider the sources already mentioned: Green Paper on alternative dispute resolution in civil and commercial matters; Directive 2008/52/EC on certain aspects of mediation in civil and commercial matters; European Commission Report of 26/8/2016 on the application of Directive 2008/52/EC; European Parliament Resolution of 12 September 2017 on the implementation of Directive 2008/52/EC.

only a little more than a decade - already appears to be highly articulated and extensively structured¹¹². Especially in the initial considerations of the European legal sources, both the strategic objectives pursued, and the main lines of action are clearly outlined, which in the consumer sphere have been delineated in a more precise and advanced manner.

The difficulties – more political than legal and technical - of building a complete and shared European system of alternative justice on a legislative, administrative and professional level, were also evident. This is the European system that, in a complementary way to jurisdiction, responds both to the social demands of facilitating the protection of the rights granted to the most vulnerable subjects, as well as to meet the economic expectations of promoting the cross-border development of the free exchange of goods and services, starting from its growing digital dimension.

Building a common system of European alternative justice implies the gradual overcoming of the more closed and conservative approaches, both national and international. It is necessary to embrace a more open and innovative vision of justice, achieved through a long and delicate regulatory path, but always respecting fundamental rights¹¹³.

A significant period must elapse to bring about a profound change in mentality not only in the political and professional circles, involved in the construction of alternative justice, but also in the entire social and economic communities in the Union, which must become more familiar with ODR mechanisms.

Only in this way could citizens and economic operators appreciate ODR's advantages and point out its critical aspects.

To establish itself, probably, the new European culture of alternative justice requires at least a generational shift, necessary for the completion of the most complex and delicate reorganisation processes that affect the very foundations of belonging to the community, which are related precisely to the idea and operation of justice with which we were born and have been educated.

In this awareness, experts in this field are also asked for a more immediate reconstructive contribution, which clarifies how to place the additional element of the present and the future European ODR system in the current phase of the legal framework of the Union. When envisaging practical solutions, however, due consideration must be given both to the wide spaces of autonomy left open by the system and to the possibility that innovative solutions that receive broad support may subsequently be adopted at the regulatory level¹¹⁴.

¹¹² P. CORTÉS, *The new regulatory framework for consumer dispute resolution*, in Oxford scholarship online, 2017.

¹¹³ S. OROMI VALLOVERA, *Institucionalización de la resolución alternativa de litigios de consumo en la Unión Europea*, in *Revista General de Derecho Europeo*, no. 36, 2015.

¹¹⁴ Looking at the development of EU discipline about mediation, the legal solution that appears to be the most relevant and practicable on a legislative and administrative level is linked to the consumer.